

TEACHING PHYSICS BASED ON MODERN INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES

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Annotation. The task of modern education is not just the communication of knowledge or the transformation of knowledge into a tool for the creative development of the world, at the present stage of the development of society, the requirements for the preservation and development of the student's personal qualities, the development of his creative potential and intelligence, life-value orientations come to the fore.

Keywords: physics, task, modern, science

The question of how to use special pedagogical means to purposefully develop the student's intellect, his creative thinking, to form a scientific worldview and an active life position remains open. This is the number one problem of modern innovative searches.

In innovative processes, the goal of learning is to develop students' opportunities to learn new experiences based on the formation of creative and critical thinking, providing conditions for such development that would allow everyone to discover and fully realize their potential: physical, spiritual and intellectual.

Let's define the term innovation processes from a historical and scientific point of view:

Innovation is an implemented innovation that provides a qualitative increase in the efficiency of processes or products demanded by the market.

The term "innovation" comes from the Latin "novatio", which means "update" (or "change") and the prefix "in", which translates from Latin as "in the direction", if translated literally "Innovatio" - "in the direction of change". The very concept of innovation first appeared in scientific research of the 19th century.

The concept of "innovation" received a new life at the beginning of the 20th century. in the scientific works of the Austrian economist J. Schumpeter as a result of the analysis of "innovative combinations", changes in the development of economic systems.

Innovation is not any innovation or innovation, but only one that seriously increases the efficiency of the current system.

Accordingly, it is necessary to clearly define and differentiate the concepts "innovative educational technologies" and "innovative education". In this way:

Innovative educational technologies and programs are any educational technologies that are the result of the innovative activities of teachers who created and developed them;

Innovative education is only those innovative educational technologies and programs where the result of the innovative activity of teachers is the creation (generation) of innovative ideas by students.

Innovative technologies for teaching physics

Innovations in education, understood in a broad sense as introducing something new, changing, improving and improving the existing one, can be called an immanent characteristic of education, arising from its main meaning, essence and significance.

The main functions of the teacher's innovative activity include progressive (so-called defect-free) changes in the pedagogical process and its components:

- 1) change in purpose;
- 2) change in the content of education;
- 3) new teaching aids;
- 4) new ideas of education;
- 5) new methods and techniques for teaching, developing, educating younger students, etc.

Depending on the area in which innovation processes take place, the following innovation processes can be distinguished:

- 1) in the content of education;
- 2) in technology;
- 3) in the organization;
- 4) in the system and management;
- 5) in educational ecology.

Innovative technologies for teaching physics (research, gaming, discussion, etc.) should include such activities of students that are characterized by their subjective position in the lesson, since the activity of students in the lesson is determined not only by the content and structure of physical knowledge, but also by their individual needs and interests.

The methodology for using innovative technologies for teaching physics will be effective if they ensure the full inclusion of students in cognitive activity in the lesson, which involves independent obtaining and analysis of results, a dialogue form of organizing search activities, a positive emotional attitude of students to the content of the lesson and their orientation towards achieving success in educational activities.

Information technology in teaching physics

My research on the application and development of innovative learning technologies began in 2004 with a study on "Introduction of information computer technologies based on the use of the software package "electronics workbench" and the creation of a system of frontal laboratory experiment for the study of electrical phenomena in grades 10-11, as one of the elements of innovative pedagogical technologies." The result of this work was the creation of a system of frontal physical experiment for the study of electrical phenomena in grades 10-11.

The system of a frontal physical experiment for the study of electrical phenomena in grades 10-11 is a combination of natural and virtual laboratory work, software and methodological support for their implementation, and creative individual tasks.

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